

Results				
Reliability Analysis				
Scale Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
scale	3.64	0.807	0.707	0.777
Item Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	If item dropped	
			Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
A1 — When making software	3.33	1.371	0.506	0.618
A2 — When making software	3.67	0.888	0.735	0.813
A3 — When making software	3.83	1.193	0.723	0.800
A4 [R] — Sustainability is not	3.83	1.337	0.502	0.645
A5 — I know how to evaluate	3.25	1.357	0.512	0.627
A6 [R] — Environmental conc	3.92	1.379	0.834	0.851
References				
[1] The jamovi project (2022). jamovi. (Version 2.3) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from https://www.jamovi.org .				
[2] R Core Team (2021). R: A Language and environment for statistical computing. (Version 4.1) [Computer software]. Retrieved from https://cran.r-project.org . (R packages retrieved from MRAN snapshot 2022-01-01).				
[3] Revelle, W. (2019). psych: Procedures for Psychological, Psychometric, and Personality Research. [R package]. Retrieved from https://cran.r-project.org/package=psych .				

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Scale Reliability Statistics							
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω			
scale	3.53	0.643	0.819	0.835			
Item Reliability Statistics							
				If item dropped			
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω			
A1- Post	3.75	1.055	0.737	0.775			
a2- post	3.75	0.866	0.839	0.856			
a3- post	4.25	0.622	0.832	0.851			
a4- post ^a	3.17	1.193	0.745	0.775			
a5- post	3.67	0.778	0.782	0.810			
a6- post ^a	2.58	0.669	0.771	0.790			

Descriptives						
	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE	
A1 — When making software design decisions, I consider environmer	12	3.33	3.00	1.371	0.396	
A1- Post	12	3.75	3.50	1.055	0.305	
A2 — When making software design decisions, I consider social impa	12	3.67	4.00	0.888	0.256	
a2- post	12	3.75	4.00	0.866	0.250	
A3 — When making software design decisions, I consider economic i	12	3.83	4.00	1.193	0.345	
a3- post	12	4.25	4.00	0.622	0.179	
A4 [R] — Sustainability is not a priority for me when developing softwa	12	2.17	2.00	1.337	0.386	
a4- post	12	1.83	1.00	1.193	0.345	
A5 — I know how to evaluate the environmental footprint of a softwar	12	3.25	3.00	1.357	0.392	
a5- post	12	3.67	3.50	0.778	0.225	
A6 [R] — Environmental concerns are someone else's responsibility ir	12	02.08	1.50	1.379	0.398	
a6- post	12	1.42	1.00	0.669	0.193	

Paired Samples T-Test									
				Statistic	p	Mean difference	SE difference		Effect Size
A1 — When making software design decisions, I consider environmer	A1- Post	Wilcoxon W		4.00	a	0.073			
A2 — When making software design decisions, I consider social impa	a2- post	Wilcoxon W		0.00	b	1.000	-1.000	0.1930	Rank biserial correlation
A3 — When making software design decisions, I consider economic i	a3- post	Wilcoxon W		4.00	d	0.198	-0.500	0.3128	Rank biserial correlation
A4 [R] — Sustainability is not a priority for me when developing softwa	a4- post	Wilcoxon W		10.00	e	0.072	1.000	0.1421	Rank biserial correlation
A5 — I know how to evaluate the environmental footprint of a softwar	a5- post	Wilcoxon W		2.00	f	0.168	-1.000	0.2599	Rank biserial correlation
A6 [R] — Environmental concerns are someone else's responsibility ir	a6- post	Wilcoxon W		18.50	d	0.106	1.000	0.3761	Rank biserial correlation

Results					
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Scale Reliability Statistics					
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω	
scale	3.69	0.478	-0.0773	0.305	
Item Reliability Statistics					
	Mean	SD	If item dropped		
			Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω	
B1 — I am aware that cognitiv	4.00	1.128	0.435	0.5921	
B2 — My design choices are	3.25	0.866	-0.161	0.2406	
B3 — I can recognise when a	3.17	0.937	-0.655	0.0697	
B4 [R] — I rarely question wh	4.33	0.985	-0.156	0.3707	
References					
[1] The jamovi project (2022). jamovi. (Version 2.3) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from https://www.jamovi.org .					
[2] R Core Team (2021). R: A Language and environment for statistical computing. (Version 4.1) [Computer software]. Retrieved from https://cran.r-project.org . (R packages retrieved from MRAN snapshot 2022-01-01).					
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Scale Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
scale	3.21	0.753	0.689	0.749
Item Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	If item dropped	
			Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
b1- post	4.17	0.718	0.690	0.797
b2-post ^a	3.67	0.985	0.776	0.822
b3-post ^a	2.58	1.165	0.466	0.595
b4-post	2.42	1.240	0.408	0.509
References				
[1] The jamovi project (2022). jamovi. (Version 2.3) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from https://www.jamovi.org .				
[2] R Core Team (2021). R: A Language and environment for statistical computing. (Version 4.1) [Computer software]. Retrieved from https://cran.r-project.org . (R packages retrieved from MRAN snapshot 2022-01-01).				
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Descriptives								
	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE			
B1 — I am aware that cognitive bias	12	4.00	4.00	1.128	0.326			
b1- post	12	4.17	4.00	0.718	0.207			
B2 [R] — My design choices are at	12	3.25	3.50	0.866	0.250			
b2-post	12	3.33	3.50	0.985	0.284			
B3 — I can recognise when a bias	12	3.17	3.00	0.937	0.271			
b3-post	12	3.42	4.00	1.165	0.336			
B4 [R] — I rarely question whether	12	2.67	2.00	0.985	0.284			
b4-post	12	2.42	2.00	1.240	0.358			

Paired Samples T-Test								
			Statistic	p	Mean difference	SE difference		Effect Size
b4-post	B4 [R] — I rarely question whether	Wilcoxon W	7.50 ^a	0.590	-0.500	0.351	Rank biserial correlation	-0.286
b3-post	B3 — I can recognise when a bias	Wilcoxon W	8.00 ^b	0.345	1.000	0.218	Rank biserial correlation	0.600
b2-post	B2 [R] — My design choices are at	Wilcoxon W	20.00 ^d	0.821	4.29e-5	0.288	Rank biserial correlation	0.111
b1- post	B1 — I am aware that cognitive bias	Wilcoxon W	16.00 ^e	0.792	7.19e-5	0.366	Rank biserial correlation	0.143

Results				
Reliability Analysis				
Scale Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
scale	3.67	0.537	0.706	0.756
Item Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	If item dropped	
			Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
C1 — I believe AI tools can help me	4.25	0.622	0.550	0.681
C2 [R] — AI-driven questionnaires	3.08	0.900	0.430	0.587
C3 — A conversational AI can help me	4.33	0.492	0.848	0.864
C4 [R] — I would rather reflect on my	3.00	0.853	0.537	0.655
References				
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Scale Reliability Statistics							
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω			
scale	03.04	0.382	0.459	0.655			
Item Reliability Statistics							
	Mean	SD	If item dropped				
			Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω			
c1-post	4.50	0.522	0.388	0.638			
c2-post	1.75	0.866	0.739	0.759			
c3-post	4.58	0.515	0.266	0.528			
c4-post ^a	1.33	0.492	0.144	0.532			

Descriptives								
	N	Mean	Median	SD	SE			
C1 — I believe AI tools can help m	12	4.25	4.00	0.622	0.179			
c1-post	12	4.50	4.50	0.522	0.151			
C2 [R] — AI-driven questioning is r	12	1.92	2.00	0.900	0.260			
c2-post	12	1.75	2.00	0.866	0.250			
C3 — A conversational AI can effe	12	4.33	4.00	0.492	0.142			
c3-post	12	4.58	5.00	0.515	0.149			
C4 [R] — I would rather reflect on i	12	2.00	2.00	0.853	0.246			
c4-post	12	1.67	2.00	0.492	0.142			

Paired Samples T-Test									
			Statistic	p	Mean difference	SE difference		Effect Size	
C1 — I believe AI tools can help m	c1-post	Wilcoxon W	0.00 ^a	0.149	-1.000	0.131	Rank biserial correlation	-1.000	
C2 [R] — AI-driven questioning is r	c2-post	Wilcoxon W	13.00 ^b	0.665	1.000	0.405	Rank biserial correlation	0.238	
C3 — A conversational AI can effe	c3-post	Wilcoxon W	3.00 ^d	0.233	-1.000	0.179	Rank biserial correlation	-0.600	
C4 [R] — I would rather reflect on i	c4-post	Wilcoxon W	12.50 ^d	0.203	1.000	0.225	Rank biserial correlation	0.667	

Results					
Reliability Analysis					
Scale Reliability Statistics					
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω	
scale	04.06	0.356	0.439	0.622	
Item Reliability Statistics					
	Mean	SD	If item dropped		
			Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω	
D1 — I regularly use AI tools	4.67	0.492	0.414	0.521	
D2 — I feel confident using A	4.58	0.669	0.316	0.628	
D3 [R] — I find AI tools difficu	2.17	0.718	0.570	0.713	
D4 — I have used conversatic	4.83	0.389	0.168	0.407	
References					
[1] The jamovi project (2022). jamovi. (Version 2.3) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from https://www.jamovi.org .					
[2] R Core Team (2021). R: A Language and environment for statistical computing. (Version 4.1) [Computer software]. Retrieved from https://cran.r-project.org . (R packages retrieved from MRAN snapshot 2022-01-01).					
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Reliability Analysis					
Scale Reliability Statistics					
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω	
scale	3.38	0.653	0.400	0.629	
Item Reliability Statistics					
	Mean	SD	If item dropped		
			Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω	
E1 — I have used AI tools to	3.42	1.443	0.0647	0.481	
E2 [R] — I believe AI has no n	2.17	0.835	0.4601	0.710	
E3 — I am interested in tools	4.50	0.522	0.1250	0.403	
E4 [R] — Sustainability and A	3.42	1.311	0.5480	0.696	
References					
[1] The jamovi project (2022). jamovi. (Version 2.3) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from https://www.jamovi.org .					
[2] R Core Team (2021). R: A Language and environment for statistical computing. (Version 4.1) [Computer software]. Retrieved from https://cran.r-project.org . (R packages retrieved from MRAN snapshot 2022-01-01).					
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Scale Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
scale	3.73	0.703	0.672	0.728
Item Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	If item dropped	
			Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
F1 — The chatbot's questions	3.83	1.030	0.402	0.554
F2 [R] — I found the convers	3.75	1.138	0.510	0.539
F3 — The chatbot's questions	4.25	0.754	0.740	0.807
F4 [R] — Interacting with the	03.08	0.996	0.663	0.762
References				
Results	F + 2 question: I noticed biases in my own reasoning during the interaction			
	I reconsidered assumptions I had not questioned before			
Reliability Analysis				
Scale Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
scale	3.78	0.648	0.852	0.866
Item Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	If item dropped	
			Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
F1 — The chatbot's questions	4.00	0.943	0.770	0.795
F2 [R] — I found the convers	3.00	0.816	0.785	0.811
F3 — The chatbot's questions	4.20	0.789	0.867	0.881
F4 [R] — Interacting with the	3.10	0.994	0.853	0.864
I noticed biases in my own re	4.10	0.738	0.858	0.873
I reconsidered assumptions I	4.30	0.823	0.808	0.833
References				
[1] The jamovi project (2022). jamovi. (Version 2.3) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from https://www.jamovi.org .				

[2] R Core Team (2021). R: A Language and environment for statistical computing. (Version 4.1) [Computer software]. Retrieved from <https://cran.r-project.org>. (R packages retrieved from MRAN snapshot 2022-01-01).

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Scale Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
scale	4.23	0.482	0.0923	0.461
Item Reliability Statistics				
	Mean	SD	If item dropped	
			Cronbach's α	McDonald's ω
G4 — After this experience, I	4.25	0.754	0.0383	0.31680
G1 — I intend to use AI refle	4.33	0.778	-0.5564	0.00674
G2 [R] — I would not use a to	04.08	1.379	0.3115	0.62197
G3 — I think tools like BIAS s	4.25	0.622	0.3105	0.68241
References				
[1] The jamovi project (2022). jamovi. (Version 2.3) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from https://www.jamovi.org .				
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